

ROBOTIC EXPLORATION MISSIONS ON THE LUNAR SURFACE

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Introduction: The exploration of the Moon has become central in the strategies of most space agencies worldwide. This is evident by the increasing number of countries joining the Artemis Accords, under which NASA is willing to return to the Moon with a long-term perspective [1]. NASA is also leading the CLPS program, through which US companies are offering robotic platforms (landers, rovers, drones) to access the lunar surface on a commercial basis. This will allow both the possibility to explore and gather important scientific data for future missions and to validate new technologies (e.g. EDS, materials, radiations shields, mobilities concepts, ISRU technologies, etc.) for a sustained presence on the Moon.

In this framework, the Italian Space Agency is currently participating in several missions both as part of the European Space Agency and at national level or in bi/multi-lateral cooperation. Among the national initiatives, ASI is promoting an Italian-led robotic exploration mission on the lunar surface. In September 2025, two competing consortia led by OHB-Italia S.p.A. and Thales Alenia Space-Italia S.p.A. completed the feasibility study of their respective concepts of lunar exploration missions. The objectives indicated by ASI were connected to exploration of areas with potential benefits for future habitability, i.e.

environmental characterization, resources prospecting. The adoption of modular architecture and use of novel mobility technologies was encouraged, as well as the cooperation in case of multiple elements. The landing capability was excluded by the study, assuming it as a commercial service or barter benefit. After 12 months of work, the consortia presented two significantly different mission scenarios, described below.

The ROMULUS mission concept, elaborated by OHB-I and its partners, focused on the exploration of the Mare Tranquillitatis Pit and the underlying lava tube [2]. The scouting activity was assigned to a legged-wheeled rover that can also execute several hops using thrusters, with the aim of going into, and possibly out, the lunar pit. Figure 1 describes surface element architecture (Lander excluded) and the nominal mission scenario, articulated into different steps with incremental ambitions and risks:

- Step 1A: exploration and sampling, going back and forth towards the lander (2 km)
- Step 1B: travel from the lander to approach the MTP (1,5km)
- Step 2: two laps around the MTP for Ground Penetrating survey (2,5km)

Figure 1 – ROMULUS (Robotic Mission to Unexplored Lunar Surface) mission concept

- Step 3: MTP descent operations, which include:
 - o Deployment of PCRS
 - o Inspection flight (500m range)
 - o Descent flight inside the MTP (100m depth)
- Step 4: Lava tube exploration

The cumulative duration of the phase is expected to be 12,3 Earth days; after, the rover switches off because it is not designed to survive the lunar night. However, since the temperature inside the lava tube should be constant around 20°C [3], the rover is conceived to have enough energy to switch on after the lunar night and to have a certain level of autonomy to re-gain DTE signal, properly re-positioning itself at the lava tube entrance, with a potential extended mission duration of 41,8 Earth days.

The robotic elements of the architecture are:

- HMLV: High Mobility Lunar Vehicle, to explore the lunar surface
- FLS: Fixed Lunar Station, to guarantee local and DTE communication with EGS
- PCRS: Portable Communication Relay System, to operate as local communications relay during the MTP exploration.

The MRSL mission concept, presented by TAS-I and its partners, targeted the exploration of a Permanent Shadowed Region (PSR) at the South Pole. The system architecture includes several robotic elements (Figure 2):

- A wheeled rover equipped with a drill and the possibility to accommodate several scientific instruments
- A legged rover
- A moon Drone
- A Common Platform Element (CPE) as interface between the lander and the various elements,

equipped with a deployment system to position the robotic elements on the lunar surface

The nominal mission lasts 84 Earth days, which is the duration of a lunar day in the surroundings of the De Gerlache Rim Region, assuming a landing in June 2031. Surface operations, whose total duration is planned to be 14 days, will include:

- Scouting by the drone, to gain information on the context (both on surface and inside PSRs)
- Scouting by legged rover, approaching the crater to evaluate the best path for the traverse of the wheeled rover
- Mapping, prospecting and drilling by the wheeled rover
- Exploration of the PSR by the drone and legged rover

The results of the studies are now under review by ASI experts, to decide on the possible follow-up. ASI is also particularly interested in potential partnerships for the next phases of this initiative.

References:

[1] S. Creech, J. Guidi and D. Elburn, "Artemis: An Overview of NASA's Activities to Return Humans to the Moon," 2022 IEEE Aerospace Conference (AERO), Big Sky, MT, USA, 2022, pp. 1-7, [2] Carer, L., Pozzobon, R., Sauro, F., Castelletti, D., Patterson, G. W., & Bruzzone, L. (2024). Radar evidence of an accessible cave conduit on the Moon below the Mare Tranquillitatis pit. *Nature Astronomy*, 8(9), 1119-1126, [3] Horvath, Tyler, Paul O. Hayne, and David A. Paige. "Thermal and illumination environments of lunar pits and caves: Models and observations from the diviner lunar radiometer experiment." *Geophysical Research Letters* 49.14 (2022)

Figure 2 – MRSL mission concept